

Development of Functional Genomics Tools in Wheat

1. Candidate's Background

I obtained Bachelor of Science degree in Plant Genetics and Microbiology from University of California at Berkeley, where I also studied bacterial quorum sensing in Steve Lindow's lab (Dulla et al. 2010). During my PhD studies at Brian Staskawicz's lab, also at UC Berkeley, I combined my interest in Plants and Microbes and focused on plant/pathogen interactions. During this time, I developed interest for computational biology. During the six years of my PhD, I took classes and became proficient in programming, statistics, and bioinformatics, including next generation sequencing technologies. In the lab, I combined molecular biology, biochemistry, genetics, and plant pathology techniques to study the basis of pathogen effector recognition in by *Arabidopsis* and successfully completed my thesis resulting in two first author and one co-first author publications (Chou et al. 2011; Krasileva et al. 2010; Krasileva et al. 2011). At the same time, I applied computational analyses to such problems as prediction of pathogen-derived effector molecules (Goritschnig et al., in press), evolutionary analyses (Zhao et al. 2011), and genome assembly (Potnis et al. 2010). As a result, I became a truly multidisciplinary scholar.

Another aspect of academic life I enjoy greatly is sharing my work with peers. In both writing and oral presentation I value clear and honest presentation of data and logical, open discussion. I was honored to deliver a talk on my PhD project at the International Society for Plant Microbe Interactions Conference in Quebec, 2009. Last month, I gladly gave a formal seminar on my PhD work at the Department of Plant Pathology at UC Davis. I enjoy sharing my research results and believe that open communication is a key element in science.

I believe that together with primary research and communication, teaching is an integral part of academia. I am member of the American Association of the Advancement of Science and I monitor current news in science, policy and education. I have a variety of teaching experiences: I developed and conducted a one day microbiology lab course for 7-8th grade kids through the university academic talent development program; taught undergraduate students general biology winning an Outstanding Graduate Student Instructor Award; and helped teach graduate student and postdocs the basics of programming. I enjoy teaching and I will gladly take opportunities to teach in the future.

2. Training / Career Development Plan

Although I was not born in the United States, I am proud to be a naturalized citizen, my family is also here, and I am dedicated to developing my career in this country. I have devoted my PhD studies at UC Berkeley to understanding the fundamental basis of plant innate immunity. In parallel, I gained extensive expertise in bioinformatics and computational biology. I believe that we need to study crop species with the same vigor as we apply to *Arabidopsis* and that next generation sequencing techniques can provide the means to do so. I plan to develop my career path in academia, and in approximately three years I hope to start my own group working in plant genomics and plant molecular biology. I envision my group having direct impact on agriculture. Understanding the coding potential of wheat genome and wheat immunity against microorganisms will be translated into development of resistant varieties and improved food products. In turn, this will create a greater food security for our growing population. As my mentor Jorge Dubcovsky holds a position as the Leader of the UC Davis Wheat Breeding Program, I will use my training years in his lab to better understand specific goals and challenges of breeding programs. This will allow me to address them with my future research. The skills and expertise I will acquire during my postdoctoral training developing genomic tools for wheat are fundamental and I will translate them to studying other agronomic species. Being a NIFA fellow will greatly help me to advance my career in science as an independent research leader. The NIFA fellowship will also provide me with funds to travel to national and international conferences and present my research. I believe that my achievements from my PhD work, including four first author and co-first author papers, contributions to five additional publications, presentations at national and international meetings, and my passion for teaching make me a strong candidate for NIFA.

3. Project Plan

I. Introduction

Wheat (*Triticum* spp.) was domesticated at the dawn of agriculture ~10,000 years ago and has since been adapted to grow in different environments throughout the world (Dubcovsky and

Dvorak, 2007). Today, wheat remains among the three most cultivated crops and is a major source of calories and protein for the human population (<http://faostat.fao.org/>). Cultivated wheat varieties were derived from two species, hexaploid *Triticum aestivum* (bread wheat) and tetraploid *Triticum turgidum* (pasta wheat) (Dubcovsky and Dvorak, 2007). Similar to many cultivated grasses, the wheat genome has undergone several interspecific hybridization and duplication events that resulted in the AABB genome of *T. turgidum* and the AABBDD - of *T. aestivum* (Dubcovsky and Dvorak, 2007). Polyploidy and the large size of the wheat genomes poses substantial challenges and, currently, a reference genome has not been completed for any wheat species. Nonetheless, recent advances in gene capture and sequencing technologies provide the means to develop functional genomic tools that are urgently needed to address multiple biotic and abiotic challenges to wheat improvement and to enable basic wheat research.

Figure 1. Tetraploid wheat *T. turgidum* Kronos (genome AABB), 2 week old seedling

Wheat provides a unique opportunity to develop reverse genetic tools: it can withstand high mutation densities of about 20 to 30 mutations per Mb (Uauy et al., 2009). The maturation of exome capture technology in wheat (Saintenac et al., 2011) and availability of high throughput sequencing provide the opportunity to sequence existing mutant populations and create an inventory of mutations for all wheat genes. To achieve this goal, my effort will focus predominantly on sequencing the exome of mutagenized tetraploid durum wheat line *T. turgidum* spp. *durum* (Figure 1). Durum wheat provides a significant advantage over hexaploid wheat in a functional genomics program because it allows rapid combination of independent mutant alleles in the ancestral A and B genomes within the same individual. The characterization of wheat mutant populations proposed here will not only provide tools to analyze the function of different wheat genes, but will also generate a huge increase in nucleotide diversity that will help breeders by providing a new source of genetic variation. **A product of my research will be a public database in which a gene can be queried and from which discovered mutant individuals**

can be obtained by a simple seed request, and this will immensely benefit basic research and breeding.

The specific aims of my proposal are:

Aim 1. Define the gene space of tetraploid wheat.

Aim 2. Capture and sequence the exome of the tetraploid wheat

Aim 3. Assemble a comprehensive mutant library of tetraploid wheat.

This work will form foundation for future projects in my own lab where I plan to utilize reverse genetics tool for dissecting disease resistance pathways in wheat.

Preliminary results

I have already achieved considerable progress on Aim 1, defining the genes of tetraploid wheat. First, I compiled information on wheat genes from publically available databases, such as TriFLdb (trifldb.psc.riken.jp) and Unigene (www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/unigene). I have merged two datasets, checked for contaminating sequences and eliminated redundancies. The resulting dataset contains approximately 16,000 non-redundant genes from hexaploid wheat. In order to get more sequences and separate homeologous gene copies into appropriate genomes, I analyzed 50 million Illumina RNA-seq sequences from tetraploid wheat, kindly provided to me by Cristobal Uauy (John Innes Center). Using both reference-based mapping and de novo approaches, I assembled a 48 Mb wheat transcriptome. This assembly represents about 25,000 to

Table 1 Transcriptome of tetraploid wheat

Sequence type	Source	# seq	Total L	Informative SNPs/DIPs
Full-length	Mapping	11,656	18 Mb	240,580
Full-length or partial with homology to rice/barley/wheat protein	Mapping/ De novo	22,691	30 Mb	~250,000
Unknown fragments	Mapping/ De novo	27,298		
Total	-	61,615	48 Mb	~500,000

30,000 genes, where A and B copies are merged together (Table 1). Around 15,000 sequences are full-length based on comparisons with annotated protein sequences in rice. In order to separate A and B gene copies, I performed single-nucleotide polymorphism (SNPs) and deletion/insertion polymorphisms (DIP) detection (Table 1). Using *samtools phase* software (Li et al., 2009) and HapCut (Bansal and Bafna, 2008), I phased SNPs to assemble A and B gene copies. The diploid rice genome contains about 40,000 genes; therefore, I can predict that I am still missing around 10,000 wheat genes, which are either not expressed or expressed at very low levels in the existing dataset. Overall, I have already made substantial progress on my Aim 1, which is a critical step in successful completion of proposed research.

II. Rationale and Significance

My proposal addresses an overdue task of simplifying and speeding up genomic studies in wheat. While genomes of major food crops, such as corn and rice, have been published, little information is currently available on wheat. Most of the initiated studies focus on whole genomes of wheat, and I want to focus on wheat coding potential as I believe it would be most useful for rapid advancement in breeding and basic research. The understanding of the gene space of wheat will improve our genome-assisted breeding strategies. The availability of fully sequenced library of induced alleles will provide unprecedented amount of information and nucleotide diversity that can be used by breeders as a source of genetic variation. Therefore, my proposed research directly addresses the AFRI Challenge Area - Food Security, and AFRI Foundation Area – Plant Health and Production of Plant Products.

III. Approach

Aim 1. Define the gene space of tetraploid wheat

Despite the large size of the wheat genome (13 Gb for tetraploid wheat), most of it is occupied by intergenic space and consists of non-coding and repetitive sequences (Cantu et al., 2010). Based upon other grass species, we estimate that each diploid genome copy in wheat contains only ~30,000 genes, a total of approximately 60 Mb for the tetraploid transcriptome. Therefore, the wheat transcriptome is amenable to deep sequencing using next generation

technologies, such as Illumina. Despite growing genomic information about hexaploid wheat, currently, there are no genome-wide gene models for any wheat species.

The initial gene prediction in tetraploid wheat requires careful transcriptome analysis. To accomplish this, we have chosen direct sequencing of transcriptome (RNA-seq) technology that provides deep coverage of transcripts and is not dependent on a reference genome. Only recently, advances in the assembly algorithms enabled *de novo* transcriptome assembly without prior information of the reference genome (Martin and Wang, 2011). Our laboratory has already generated sequencing data corresponding to about 10-15X coverage of tetraploid wheat transcriptome from wheat tissues using Illumina technology. In addition, the 1.5 million 454 reads from hexaploid wheat and its draft transcriptome assembly is available. In order to complete high-quality transcriptome assembly for the tetraploid wheat, I will construct additional libraries for RNA-seq from different plant tissues, including wheat seedlings, mature leaf blade and leaf spike. These libraries will have features specifically suited for transcriptome assembly, such as amenability to paired-end sequencing, short and long insert sizes (300 bp and 500 bp) and mRNA enrichment. In order to uncover rare transcripts, I will perform library normalization using the CRAB duplex DNA nuclease to deplete highly abundant transcripts (Christodoulou et al., 2011). Before the assembly, I will pre-process all of the sequencing data to remove artifacts, such as adaptors, low-complexity reads, remaining rRNA and other RNA contaminants.

In total, we plan to achieve >30X coverage of the entire wheat transcriptome, which can be directly used for transcript assembly. I plan to tackle the problem of transcriptome assembly of tetraploid wheat using the “align-then-assemble” method, a combinatorial approach of reference-based and *de novo* prediction (Martin and Wang, 2011) (Figure 2). This approach combines the sensitivity of reference-based strategy, enabling the assembly of low abundance transcripts with the freedom of *de novo* assembly. The first step of the assembly will be mapping of the reads to

Figure 2. Pipeline for gene prediction in tetraploid wheat

the available hexaploid wheat genomic and EST data using CLC Genomics Workbench and TopHat aligners (Trapnell et al., 2009). Resulting pre-assembled reads will be combined with reads that did not map (due to polymorphisms or gaps in the existing data) and passed to the *de novo* transcriptome assembly programs, CLC Genomics Workbench and Trans-ABYSS (Birol et al., 2009), that support both long and short reads. I will evaluate the quality of transcriptome assembly using several parameters. A benchmark dataset of wheat genes with experimentally validated gene models is available from previous functional studies in the Dubcovsky laboratory and will be used to estimate the false positive and false negative error rates at each step of the method. Using well-annotated rice and *Brachypodium* genes I will evaluate how many transcripts are assembled at full length. Finally, the resulting assembly will be mapped back to currently available genomic sequence of closely related species (barley, rice, *Brachypodium*) to extend transcripts and infer gene models using TopHat (Trapnell et al., 2009) and Exonerate programs (Slater and Birney, 2005).

Figure 3. Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms in the Illumina data indicate the differences between A and B copies of a wheat gene

Gene prediction in polyploid species is challenging; however, we have all the tools to make substantial progress within next year. Variations of the proposed gene prediction strategy have already been successfully implemented for *de novo* transcriptome assembly of different organisms (Martin and Wang, 2011). A challenge in gene prediction in polyploidy wheat is to separate different homeologs (AA and BB). Software developed to phase heterozygous haplotypes, such as *samtools phase* (Li et al., 2009) and HapCut (Bansal and Bafna, 2008) can be directly adapted to infer A and B gene copies in wheat. If there is a substantial number of homeologs that we cannot distinguish, I will sequence a transcriptome of a closely related diploid wheat species *T. urartu* (AA genome, 99% identical), which will allow unambiguous gene assignment. The initial set of transcripts and gene models would serve as a template for designing probes for exome capture (Aim 2). After the first round of exome capture is accomplished, I will expand and update our predicted gene models. Specifically, these iterations will help me to resolve gene models that have several collapsed homologous genes. We plan to maintain close communication with groups developing gene models in barley and hexaploid wheat for the most rapid and effective advancements in completing this Aim.

Completion of this Aim will present a major achievement in the field. Using RNA-seq, I will be able to surpass the need of the full reference genome (where gene space occupies only 0.5% of total DNA) to allow functional genetic and proteomic studies.

Potential Pitfalls

Genomic datasets are never fully inclusive; therefore, I expect that I will miss some genes. I expect that my initial dataset will be updated as we gain more information. I can measure completeness of my set against genomes of rice and sorghum. Overall, I feel that taking this project further even with 30,000 genes (60,000 counting A and B copies) will be appropriate. Remaining genes can be sequenced in smaller follow-up studies using the pipeline that I will establish.

Aim 2. Capture and sequence the exome of tetraploid wheat

Recently published studies established that gene capture combined with next-generation sequencing is suitable for wheat (Saintenac et al., 2011; Tsai et al., 2011) (Table 2). I will extend the gene capture technique to cover whole exome of tetraploid wheat.

The transcriptome assembly produced in Aim 1 will serve as a starting point in the probe design. Since the AA and BB genomes of wheat are very closely related (~97% identity), initially, one set of probes can be used to capture both diploid genomes. I will identify the most divergent gene copies (such as disease resistant genes) and include them separately in the probe design. I will use the probe design provided by Nimblegen and their DNA/DNA hybridization strategy to cover the full wheat transcriptome. Captured DNA will be subsequently sequenced using the Illumina technology. For the initial

experiment, I will use full-length transcripts for designing the baits, so that some probes will capture intronic DNA. This will provide experimental support for the predicted gene models and will allow us to create and update models that are unavailable or incorrect.

In the final experimental design, I will make the probes to capture and sequence exons only, thereby, reducing number of probes needed for most efficient capture. Successful completion of this Aim will lead to the experimentally validated probe set that could be used for exome capture not only of our reference line, *T. turgidum* spp. *durum* variety ‘Kronos’, but also other wheat lines. Therefore, it will provide a tool that could be used by wheat researchers and wheat breeders for the rapid genotyping of multiple wheat varieties.

Potential Pitfalls

Gene capture is becoming a mature technology. It has been successfully applied to crops species, including wheat, therefore, I do not envision any major technical difficulties. I have already met with Key Account Manager at NimbleGen, Patrick Eimerman and discussed this project with him in detail. However, one limitation of gene capture is that it is designed against the target dataset, and will not recover genes de novo. However, gene capture has a capacity to recover diverging gene family members (up to 90% identity) as well as up to 100-200 bp of the adjacent sequences not included in the analyses (Asan et al. 2011).

Table 2. Summary of the preliminary capture-and-sequence experiment targeting 3,497 wheat genes

Wild type	9.25 M reads (46% mapped)
Mutagenized (1 individual)	8.64 M reads (44 % mapped)
Number of targeted genes	3,497
Total sequence length	~3.5M
Coverage	55% with >10 reads
Coverage threshold for	
Identification of mutations	20X
Average mutation density	1 in 33 kb

Aim 3. Assemble a comprehensive mutant library of tetraploid wheat.

Polyploid plants, such as wheat, are extremely tolerant to a high density of mutations. Our lab has a unique collection of ethyl methanesulfonate (EMS) mutagenized tetraploid wheat lines (Uauy et al., 2009). A high quality DNA samples are already available from 2,500 mutant individuals. Recently, a TILLING-by-sequencing study based on 5 target genes from 768 mutagenized individuals validated that high throughput sequencing methods can be successfully applied to sequence and identify mutations in tetraploid wheat (Tsai et al., 2011). However, current approaches have been limited to a small set of target genes and required the design of genome-specific probes. A comprehensive sequencing project and construction of a maintained wheat mutant database will eliminate this problem. I propose to capture the whole exome of tetraploid wheat and sequence up to a 1,000 of mutagenized individuals, which will produce multiple mutant alleles for each gene in wheat genome. Sequencing support for this project is available through the Howard Hughes Medical Institute grant to Dr. Dubcovsky.

a) Sequencing mutant individuals and assigning mutations

Preliminary characterization of the wheat mutant library estimated an average mutation density of 1 in 33 kbs (Table 2). Thus, by sequencing 1,000 individual mutagenized plants, we should obtain a knockout allele for each gene, plus multiple missense mutations that could lead to gain of function phenotypes. I will apply the capture-and-sequence protocol developed in Aims 1 and 2 to sequence the mutant wheat library. I will start by characterizing 20 mutant individuals, and eventually scale up towards the goal of one thousand plants.

First of all, I will directly evaluate the effectiveness of identification of mutations based on exome capture targeted at the genomic DNA in comparison to sequencing the mutant lines by RNA-seq. We expect exome capture to be a more effective approach than RNA-seq because a) it would allow capturing genes and homeologs independent of level and time of expression b) it would provide additional nucleotide variation in parts of captured introns assisting in proper assignment of homeologs to AA and BB genomes. However, RNA-seq has an advantage of eliminating the hybridization step, which is currently 60% efficient (Saintenac et al., 2011). Additionally, gene capture will not discriminate between functional gene copies and pseudo-genes

introducing noise to the system. However, a direct comparison between these technologies is needed to evaluate their relative costs and benefits. I will perform both RNA-seq and capture-and-sequence experiments on 20 mutagenized plants before we scale up the procedure.

The pipeline downstream of sequencing will present a basic single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) identification optimized for uncovering EMS mutations (Missirian et al., 2011; Saintenac et al., 2011). The sequencing reads will be filtered for contamination, and high quality reads will be aligned to the reference wheat transcriptome. The SNP identification will be performed using the existing pipelines (Missirian et al., 2011; Saintenac et al., 2011; Tsai et al., 2011). The SNPs will be filtered to yield potential EMS mutations (GC>TA) and the posterior probability of the mutation over sequencing noise will be calculated using appropriate algorithms (Missirian et al., 2011; Saintenac et al., 2011; Tsai et al., 2011). I will evaluate the amount of non-sense mutations that can be recovered for each gene. Additionally, the amino acid change mutations will be prioritized based on their predicted ability to disrupt proteins function, using the SIFT (Ng and Henikoff, 2003) and ParseSNP programs (Taylor and Greene, 2003).

Sequencing one thousand mutated wheat individuals is an ambitious project; being in Jorge Dubcovsky's lab and near the UC Davis Genomics Center puts me in a unique position to complete it. We will work together with the Genome Center at UC Davis in order to automate DNA/RNA extraction and library construction. I will also provide training to at least two undergraduate students and/or a technician to aid me in RNA/DNA extractions and library constructions. I think that we can easily achieve a goal of several hundreds of samples and set up a platform for further expansion. The end product of this Aim will be a comprehensive database of wheat mutants available to researchers worldwide and enabling genome-wide reverse genetics analyses as well as enriching wheat germplasm for breeding.

Potential Pitfalls

The most challenging part of this section will be scaling up to achieve the goal of sequencing 1,000 plants. Dubcovsky's lab already has high quality DNA isolated from 2,500 individual mutant lines. Emerging robotic technology allows rapid and automatic generation of libraries. Roche Nimblegen & Caliper Life Science recently came out with the optimized SeqCap EZ Library solution-based capture method that allows automated generation of 288 enriched

libraries per week (<http://www.nimblegen.com/redirects/promos/caliper/index.html>). This technology will allow us to achieve the stated goal over a period of two to three months.

b) Detecting functional mutations in genes involved in plant innate immunity

Development of the reverse genomics tools in wheat will provide a unique opportunity for functional studies. During my PhD work with Dr. Brian Staskawicz I gained extensive expertise in the innate immunity of *Arabidopsis* and I am interested in applying this knowledge to wheat. Knowing the transcriptome and proteome of wheat, as well as having a powerful collection of mutants, I will transfer functional information from model plant systems to wheat. Initially, I plan to focus on two major classes of proteins involved in pathogen surveillance: 1) the pattern recognition receptors, often encoded as Receptor Like Kinases (RLKs) and 2) the Resistance genes (R-genes) (Jones and Dangl, 2006). The RLKs in plants are involved in perception of common pathogen-derived molecules, similar to the innate immunity in vertebrates (Jones and Dangl, 2006). The R-genes encode a class of proteins that monitor a diverse range of pathogen-derived molecules (Jones and Dangl, 2006). Wheat transcriptome that I have already assembled contains at least 171 canonical R-genes marked by a central Nucleotide-Binding Site Domain (NBS). An alignment in Figure 4 shows that the key functional motifs in the NBS domain are conserved between *Arabidopsis* and wheat (Figure 4).

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RPP1-WsB          40 DEVRMIGIIVGPPGIGKTTIARFLFNQ--VSDRFQLSAIMVNIKGCYP 84
Ta_cDNA_1491.1   48 KDRKVLISIVGFGGLGKTTLANEVYRK--IERHFDCQAFVSVSQKPIVI 92
Ta_cDNA_1775.1   46 MKLKVFISIVGFGGLGKTTLAMEVCRQ--LEADFQRQAQVSVSQAFDG 90
Ta_cDNA_2057.1   43 EQLKVVAIVGVAGIGKTTLALKLLGK--LQQGFECDAFVRTAQKPNM 87
Ta_cDNA_3155.1   46 KQLTVLPDIVGPGGVGKTTFTQHIFEE--VKSSFQVAIWICVSLNFVA 90
Ta_cDNA_1344.1   17 EKLVVSVIVGFGGLGKTTLANQVYHK--LKGGFHCDAFVPSVQKPNM 61
Ta_cDNA_1819.1   43 QQTKLVAIVGFGGLGKTTIANQVYQE--LKGQFEYRAFLSVSRNPDI 87
Ta_cDNA_1816.1   43 KKLKVSVIVGFGGLGKTTLANQVYDD--LEGQFDCKAFIPVSVQKPDV 87
Ta_cDNA_1382.1   47 QRLKVISIVGFGGLGKTTLANEVYCK--LEGQFQCRAFVSLSQQPDV 91
Ta_cDNA_3804.1   60 DGVAVLAILGMGGVGKTTLAQVVYNDQRVLDHFDLRMWWCLPESPDV 106
Ta_cDNA_1389.1   47 YQLKVSVIVGTGGLGKTTLARQVYNK--IGANFDCRAFVPISRSPDM 91

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Figure 4. Conserved functional P-loop motif in the NBS domains of an *Arabidopsis* resistance protein RPP1 and several putative wheat proteins. Conserved amino acids are highlighted in blue.

I will develop automatic pipelines to annotate the mutations occurring in wheat RLKs and R-genes based on the functional information available from *Arabidopsis* and rice. Examples

include several known functional motifs in the nucleotide binding site domain (NBS) of R-genes (such as P-loop and MHD motifs) that are likely to produce gene knockouts (Figure 4) and mutations in the Leucine Rich Repeats domains that will allow diversification of pathogen recognition (Bendahmane et al., 2002).

Understanding the fundamental principles of wheat immunity is critical for heuristic and durable strategies of pathogen control. Devastating strains of wheat pathogens are causing epidemics across Africa and have threatened security of the crop worldwide (<http://www.fao.org/>). Chemical control of pathogens is expensive, unsustainable and sometimes unavailable to many developing countries. Therefore, genome-assisted wheat breeding has a direct impact on food security. My long-term goal is to form my own research group that will utilize genomic and functional information in wheat to study the fundamental principles of plant innate immunity and provide approaches for engineering durable disease resistance.

Proposed project timeline

The scope of the project is ambitious, yet I am confident that I have all the tools to make a substantial progress on all of the aims in the next two years. Below is a timeline for this project:

Aim	Six months	Six months	Six months	Six months
Define the genes of tetraploid wheat	>			
Develop gene capture of wheat exome	>	>>		
Sequence mutant populations		>	>>>	>>>
Survey functional mutations in disease resistance genes	>	>>	>>>	>>>>

I currently have a profile on LinkedIn, the professional networking site. I will update my progress on this site.

4. Mentoring Plan

I have gained extensive expertise in plant pathology and a foundation for bioinformatics research during my PhD. In my postdoctoral training, I want to get more experience studying wheat, a crop species, and become an expert in plant genomics. Dr. Jorge Dubcovsky is a leader

in wheat research. He is a tenured professor, a Howard Hughes Medical Institute Investigator and a Leader of the UC Davis Wheat Breeding and Regional Testing Program. Dr. Dubcovsky believes that his lab is a perfect place for me to be trained to become a next generation agricultural leader. There are three most important things I need to learn during my training in his lab: 1) wheat biology 2) translational research, i.e. how we, as researchers at a university, can help to advance agriculture; 3) establishing myself as a leader in the scientific community. I have talked with Dr. Dubcovsky about my mentoring plan and it is clear that he has perfect expertise to help me achieve these goals. Dr. Dubcovsky has twenty years of experience in wheat research, including physiology, classical genetics, as well as genomics and transcriptomics. During our daily meetings, I have already learned a lot about wheat biology. Being a Leader of the UC Davis Wheat Breeding, Dr. Dubcovsky is an established expert in applied research, addressing current agricultural problems, such as yield, drought resistance, and disease resistance. He has all the necessary experience and is willing to provide me training in translational research. Finally, Dr. Dubcovsky has a great record of training new scientist. I could see that Jorge is very supportive of his current and former postdocs and he played a big role in helping them establish themselves as independent scientists. A list of Dr. Dubcovsky's former mentees includes:

- Cristobal Uauy (PhD student and postdoc): Project Leader at the John Innes Institute
- Liuling Yan (Postdoc): Associate professor in Oklahoma State University
- Assaf Distelfeld (Postdoc): Assistant Professor in Tel Aviv University
- Viviana Echenique (Postdoc): Professor at the Univesidad Nacional del Sur (Argentina)
- Daolin Fu (postdoc): Professor at Shandong University, China

I have spoken openly with Jorge about my plans in academia. He showed strong support of my goals and assured me that he will provide the assistance necessary to develop my own project and start my own lab. He encourages me to communicate my results with colleagues outside of his lab; he supports me going to the conferences and we have already talked about specific plans for publication. In conclusion, I believe that Dr. Dubcovsky will provide me with outstanding mentorship and will help me to become a leader in agricultural research.

5. Evaluation Plan

I will measure my progress with generation of major results and datasets and their publication in scientific journals. The milestones I am setting are:

1. **Defining the sequences of wheat genes.** Completion of this dataset will be measured against total number of genes in rice. I will evaluate how many genes in my assembly are full length and how many can be separated into A and B homeologues. I already have a benchmark dataset of wheat genes that I will use to define false positive and false negative error rates in gene assembly.
2. **Successful gene-capture.** I will measure the success of gene capture through capture efficiency (% targets captured).
3. **Successful application of gene-capture to sequence wheat mutants.** I will measure how many mutations per gene are identified as we increase our sequencing sample. My goal is to provide at least one knockout allele in >90% of the genes.
4. **Annotated dataset of genes and induced alleles involved in disease resistance.** I will curate genes involved in plant disease resistance. My goal is to create a functional knockout allele in each gene and to identify possible gain of function alleles based on current information from *Arabidopsis*.

Data dissemination plan

I will make the data generated in this project fully available to the public. All of my draft datasets will be available upon request even before publication. I will publish finalized results in peer-reviewed journals, submit supplemental datasets and facilitate dissemination of next-generation sequencing data. Additionally, I will create a genome browser to display annotated information on wheat genes and sequenced mutant alleles. Corresponding wheat seed stocks will be available upon request.